

The sub- to supersolidus transition in the Lys-Caillaouas massif and Gavarnie-Héas valleys, central Pyrenees

De Leijer N.J.M.¹, Jordan D.A.A.² and Kriegsman L.M.^{1,2*}

1. Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Dept. of Research & Education, Leiden, Netherlands

2. Utrecht University, Faculty of Geosciences, Dept. of Earth Sciences, Netherlands

Partial melting is the key factor in crustal differentiation processes and in the transfer of many critical metals from the deepest continental crust to shallower levels via granitoids. These processes are documented in deeply exposed migmatite and granulite domains of former mountain belts. Migmatites are sites of melt production, but they are also affected by melt influx from deeper (granulite-dominated) levels. Additionally, the restitic units and the crystallizing melts frequently react at microscale and outcrop scale, which leaves a retrograde overprint on the peak mineral assemblages. Well-exposed areas showing the transition from subsolidus to supersolidus processes are required in order to quantify element transfers.

This project* focuses on the western Lys-Caillaouas massif and the adjacent Gavarnie-Héas valleys in the central Pyrenees, that expose a Hercynian window below an Alpine nappe stack. The area shows the transition from medium-grade metasediments to migmatites along a steep geothermal gradient. The presentation will highlight petrological and microtextural features of this transition, and addresses the geochemical link between in-situ melts in the migmatites and cross-cutting cordierite-bearing (leuco-)granites. The complexities of prograde melt-producing reactions and retrograde melt-consuming reactions will be summarized in a conceptual model for melt-mediated fluid transfer and recycling at sample and outcrop scale. This model serves as the foundation for quantifying element fluxes, including trace element redistribution.

*(*Part of the FluidNET research and training network on fluid-rock interaction, funded by EU's Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant 956127.)*